

Existence of odd prime divisors of sums of squares of two different non zero integers

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Subject : theorem with proof

Preface

This is a theorem proven by me.

Hope it will contribute to the progress of mathematics.

*I dedicate this work to every lover of pure mathematics
in the world.*

Habib Lebsir

Theorem:

Every whole number, sum of squares of two different non zero integers, has at least one odd and prime divisor, itself sum of squares of two integers prime between themselves.

$$i. e: \forall a, b : a \neq 0, b \neq 0, a \neq b$$

$$\exists \rho \neq 2 \text{ Prime number}$$

$$\rho = x^2 + y^2, \rho / a^2 + b^2$$

For some integers x, y prime between themselves

The proof of this theorem calls upon the followings:

Property ①:

Let a, b two integers prime between themselves.

We have:

Either: $a^2 + b^2 = 2N$ for some odd number N

Or: $a^2 + b^2 = 4N + 1$ for some non zero integer N

Proof: since a and b are prime between themselves they can't be both even integers: thus either both a and b are odd integers.

$$i. e a = 2k + 1, b = 2k' + 1 \text{ for some integer } k \text{ and } k'$$

$$\text{Then: } a^2 + b^2 = (2k + 1)^2 + (2k' + 1)^2 = 4k^2 + 4k'^2 + 4k + 4k' + 2 = (2k^2 + 2k'^2 + 2k + 2k' + 1) = 2N$$

$$\text{with: } 2k^2 + 2k'^2 + 2k + 2k' + 1 = N$$

N is an odd integer.

Or : a is even, b is odd.

$$i. e: a = 2k, b = 2k' + 1 \text{ for some integers } k, \text{ and } k' (k \neq 0)$$

$$\text{Then : } a^2 + b^2 = 4k^2 + 4k'^2 + 4k' + 1 = 4(k^2 + k'^2 + k') + 1 = 4N + 1 \text{ with : } N = k^2 + k'^2 + k'$$

(N is a non zero integer because $k \neq 0$).

Property ②

Let p be a prime number: $p \neq 2$.

If $p = x^2 + y^2$ for some integers x, y .

Then: x and y are prime between themselves

Proof: Indeed if $d \neq 1$ is a common divisor of x and y we will have:

$$x = dx', y = dy', x^2 + y^2 = d^2(x'^2 + y'^2)$$

Then: d^2/p which is prime.

$$\text{Thus } d^2 = p.$$

Hence $1, d$ and d^2 would be divisors of p Absurd! (Because p is prime)

Theorem ①

Every number which divides a sum of squares of two integers prime between themselves is itself sum of squares of two integers

Theorem ②

Every prime number of the form $4n + 1$ (n non zero integer) can be written as a sum of squares of two integers in only one way

Theorem ③

A prime number of the form $4n + 3$ (n Integer) can not be written as a sum of two squares of two integers

Proof of the theorem

✓ Notice that if ($a \neq 0, b \neq 0$) then $a^2 + b^2 \neq 1$ ($a^2 + b^2 \geq 2$).

The proof has two parts

☞ **Part one:** a and b are not prime between themselves i.e : $gcd(a, b) = \Delta \neq 1$

We have $a = \Delta a' \rightarrow a^2 = \Delta^2 a'^2$

$b = \Delta b' \rightarrow b^2 = \Delta^2 b'^2$

$a^2 + b^2 = \Delta^2(a'^2 + b'^2)$

If $(a'^2 + b'^2)$ is prime then the problem is solved; $(a'^2 + b'^2) | a'^2 + b'^2$ and $a'^2 + b'^2$ is sum of two squares a' and b' prime between themselves

If $a'^2 + b'^2$ is not prime.

Either: $a'^2 + b'^2 = 2N$ with N odd number; $N/a'^2 + b'^2$ and so $N/a^2 + b^2$

If N is prime, N is a sum of squares of two integers (see theorem ①)

These two integers are prime between themselves (see property ②)

if: N is not prime :

Then all its prime factors are $(4n + 1)$ prime numbers because a $(4n + 3)$ prime number can not divide $(a'^2 + b'^2)$ otherwise, it would be written as a sum of squares of two integers. (see theorem ③)

So: all the prime factors of $a'^2 + b'^2$ are sums of squares of two integers prime between themselves (see theorem ① and property ②)

Or: $a^2 + b^2 = 4N + 1$: then all its prime factors are $4n+1$ prime numbers and thus squares of two different non zero Integer prime between themselves (see theorems ② and ③ and property ②)

☞ **Finally:** if a and b are not prime between themselves $(a^2 + b^2)$ has at least one odd and prime divisor sum of squares of two integers prime between themselves.

Examples :

1) $18^2 + 12^2 = 6^2(3^2 + 2^2) = 6^2 \cdot 13$

13 is prime ; $\gcd(3,2) = 1$

$\gcd(18,12) = 6.$

2) $2^2 + 6^2 = 2^2(1^2 + 3^2) = 2^2 \times 10 = 2^2 \times 2 \times 5 = 2^3 \times 5$; $5 = 1^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

3) $20^2 + 15^2 = 5^2(4^2 + 3^2) = 5^2 \times 25 = 5^2 \times 5^2 = 5^4(5 = 1^2 + 2^2)$, $\gcd(20,15) = 5$ $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

4) $12^2 + 21^2 = 3^2(4^2 + 7^2) = 3^2 \times 65 = 3^2 \times 13 \times 5$ $\gcd(12,21) = 3$

$13 = 3^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(3,2) = 1$

$5 = 1^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

Part two : a and b prime between themselves**Section A** : a and b are both odd numbers.

$a = 2k + 1$, $b = 2k' + 1$ then :

$a^2 + b^2 = 2N$ with N is an odd number (see property ①)

 $N/a^2 + b^2$ then N is sum of squares of two integers x, y If N is prime : then x, y are prime between themselves (see property ②)**If N is not prime** :Since N is an odd number, all its prime number factors are $(4n + 1)$ prime numbers because $(4n + 3)$ prime numbers can not divide $a^2 + b^2$ otherwise they would be sums of squares**Thus** : all prime factors of N are sums of squares of two integers prime between themselves (see property ②)**Examples**:

1) $3^2 + 5^2 = 34 = 2 \times 17 = 2(1^2 + 4^2)$; $\gcd(3,5) = 1$, $\gcd(1,4) = 1$; $N = 17$

2) $11^2 + 9^2 = 202 = 2 \times (101) = 2 \times (1^2 + 10^2)$; $\gcd(11,9) = 1$, $\gcd(1,10) = 1$; $N = 101$

3) $3^2 + 11^2 = 130 = 2 \times 65$; $\gcd(3,11) = 1$, $N = 65 = 5 \times 13$

$5 = 1^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

$13 = 2^2 + 3^2$; $\gcd(2,3) = 1$

Section B: a is even, b is odd.

i.e : $a = 2k$; $b = 2k' + 1$ with k, k' integers, $k \neq 0$.

Them: $a^2 + b^2 = 4n + 1$ For some non-zero integer n (see property ①)If $4n + 1$ is not prime. $4n + 1$ is an odd number then all its prime factors are $(4n + 1)$ prime numbers because $(4n + 3)$ prime numbers can not divide $a^2 + b^2$, otherwise they would be sums of squares of two integers (see theorem ③)**Therefore**: all its prime factors are sums of squares of two integers prime between themselves (see property ① and property ②).

Examples :

1) $2^2 + 3^2 = 13$; $\gcd(2,3) = 1$

13 is prime

2) $2^2 + 11^2 = 125 = 5^3(5 = 1^2 + 2^2)$; $\gcd(2,11) = 1$ $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

3) $6^2 + 7^2 = 85 = 5 \times 17$; $\gcd(6,7) = 1$, $17 = 1^2 + 4^2$; $\gcd(1,4) = 1$
 $5 = 1^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

Finally: the theorem is proven

➤ The theorems ①, ② and ③ have been proven by Leonhard Euler and Pierre de Fermat.